

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART VII. HYDROLYSIS OF SOME ALIPHATIC ESTERS

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Hydrolysis of butyl and amyl formate, acetate, propionate and butyrate has been carried out using acetone-dried lipase in order to study the effect of change of the number of carbon atoms in the acid on the hydrolysis of esters by lipase.

The hydrolysis of butyl and amyl formate, acetate, propionate and butyrate by ricinus lipase was carried out in order to study the effect of change of the number of carbon atoms in the acid on the enzymic hydrolysis of esters. The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

Esters.	Percentage hydrolysis on days					
	1 st.	2 nd.	3 rd.	4 th.	5 th.	6 th.
Butyl formate	20.9	22.9	29.8	34.0	33.2	—
„ acetate	19.8	25.7	32.4	35.3	35.0	—
„ propionate	20.4	24.7	31.2	34.5	33.6	—
„ butyrate	21.2	23.8	30.9	33.7	32.3	—
Amyl formate	10.8	19.2	23.2	28.2	30.9	—
„ acetate	16.1	20.8	31.8	30.4	—	—
„ propionate	14.9	25.8	33.7	32.5	—	—
„ butyrate	19.8	28.1	29.2	31.2	30.5	—

From the above table the maximum percentage hydrolysis is found to be almost the same in case of all the four esters in each group and so it can be inferred that the change of the number of carbon atoms in the acid does not affect the percentage hydrolysis of esters. In other words, the hydrolysis of esters is independent of the number of carbon atoms in the acid and only depends upon the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol.